

TERRITORIAL FEATURES OF THE ORGANIZATION OF SETTLEMENTS

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In the territorial location of settlements, the appropriation of the earth's surface by people is considered a very long-lasting historical process, and it is directly related to the appropriation of the territory. Based on this, it is possible to observe the influence of ethno-ecological regions based on the above-mentioned elevation steps in the emergence of settlements in the Fergana Valley. It is noted in the literature that the exploitation was started by the population engaged in animal husbandry, horticulture, crafts and dry farming in the upper, third and partly fourth ethno-ecological regions of the valley [1, 2, 3].

In the oldest Chinese written sources, there are 70 "cities" in Ferghana, in which 60,000 families or 300,000 inhabitants lived. [5, 6]. It can be seen that most of these cities are located in the fourth, third ethno-ecological region of the Fergana Valley. In the settlements of these regions, the population was mainly engaged in animal husbandry, dry farming and mountain gardening. After the semi-sedentary life of the cattle-breeding population began to be observed, it was observed that they moved to the lower parts of the valley and prepared a separate place for themselves for the village. In such settlements, settlements of the population in the form of fortresses have been formed. We can see that the word "fortress" is often included in their names [5, 6, 7]. Such "fortifications" are in the form of crowded villages with developed trade and handicrafts in the winter months, while in other months it was observed that the majority of the population moved to the mountain pastures. More than 100 place names with the words "kurgan" and "kurgan" were recorded in our toponymic studies conducted in the region of the Fergana valley where the mountain, hill, and desert

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landscapes are connected. These mound-shaped settlements are more characteristic of the herding population of the peninsular Kyrgyz, Kipchak, Turk, and Karakalpok, and they are usually built near villages inhabited by Uzbeks and Tajiks engaged in agriculture. S.S. Gubaeva (1983) pointed out that most of these names are named after the clan or clan elder that formed it. In our preliminary studies, it was possible to identify ethnonyms such as Nogaykurgan, Kipchakkurgan, Kyrgyzkurgan, Kazakkurgan, and anthroponyms such as Torakurgan, Khankurgan, Khojakurgan, Yusufkurgancha, Sufikurgan. Also, in this region of the Fergana Valley, the toponyms of Kyzilkurgan, Ortakurgan, Qazikurgan are found 2 times, Karakurgan, Tepakurgan 3 times, Uchkurgan, Tashkurgan 4 times, Yangikurgan, Kurgantepa 5 times, and the toponym of Kurgancha 12 times.

From an ecological point of view, it can be seen that the ethno-ecological law put forward by L. N. Gumilev (1990) about the occurrence of such settlements on the border of two, in some cases, three landscape regions is fully expressed in the Fergana Valley. Settlements that appeared during the research period began to form at the junctions of hilly, mountainous and desert landscapes. Such settlements as Koson, Chodak, Akhsi, Osh, Aravon, Ershi, Kuva, Ozgan, Pop can be cited as examples [7, 8, 9]. In settlements with such different landscape zones, the amount of anthropogenic pressure on nature with the increase in population has been taken into account. In these areas, pastures, "forest-gardens" used in mountain horticulture, and lands in dryland farming were prevented from decreasing in productivity and degradation. Settlements of nomadic, semi-nomadic and sedentary populations based on the use of each landscape zone in accordance with its "nature" have emerged.

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